

A Corporate Governance Case Study Of Credit Suisse

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INTRODUCTION

The foundation of Credit Suisse marked a crucial waypoint in the history of Switzerland towards industrialisation. This paper explores the history and current affairs of Credit Suisse, arguably one of the most fabled institutions in Switzerland, with keen perspectives on corporate governance. It argues that while there has been a string of scandals that befell the bank questioning its integrity, morality, reputation, and operational soundness, the accountability and responsibility equally rest on its political and cultural environment (Guex, 2000; Hurst, 2008; McGrath, 2020; Revil, 2022).

This discourse is inextricably entrenched with the history of the modern confederacy of Switzerland: its foundation, early phases as a corporation, influence in national legislation, impact on the economy, and its transformations. Next, as with any storied journey with its ups and downs, we outline recent controversies, challenges, and scandals, the changes enacted throughout, and understand it from the viewpoint of corporate governance, both the broader and deeper sense whenever theories and practices are relevant. Finally, we opine on policy considerations relevant to Credit Suisse as it charts its future, within the organisation, its immediate political and economic circumstances, and towards the undeniable impact it has on the world at large.

HISTORY

Credit Suisse is a leading Swiss bank in the world. Established in 1856 by a Swiss politician and business leader, Alfred Escher, Credit Suisse was built to serve the immense financing required for the core civil transport and energy infrastructure in Switzerland. It also extended this finance apparatus to funding the national electrical grid and other European railway networks (Credit Suisse, 2022; Jung, 2009; Meier et al, 2013). In parallel with commercial and nation-building interests, the political-economic perspective that Escher espoused considered the sovereign independence from influence by France in the construction of Switzerland's critical infrastructure (Meier et al, 2013; Pohl, 1994).

From its origins, we observe that the aim of Credit Suisse, as a public joint-stock corporation, is intimately tied to long-term developments serving state-level and regional geopolitical missions (Clarke, 2004; Jung, 2009). While corporate governance has not reached mainstream attention and contemporary definitions then (OECD, 2021), it was founded as a strong purpose-driven corporation as we know it today (Cadbury, 1992; Clarke, 2004; Clarke, 2014; Credit Suisse Group, 2022).

In parallel, socio-political, state, and cultural sensitivities (Guex, 2000) were essential drivers in why, when, and how Credit Suisse was instituted. Corporate governance theories and history suggest a chronological evolution of the corporation from competitive capitalist of small firms to managerial capitalist and other complex legal and structural corporate forms (Cheffins, 2013; Clarke, 2014; Haldane 2015). In the case of Credit Suisse, it is evident in its rudimentary conception, it already aimed for far-reaching missions that are multi-generational in nature and whose evolving structure required the abstraction of shareholders from governance and management of the organisation (Franks & Nunnally, 2010, p.198).

Apart from transport and railways infrastructure, Credit Suisse exerted its influence in the economic, business, military, and political spheres (Franks & Nunnally, 2010, p.198; Hausman et al, 2008, p.98; Meier et al, 2013, p.89; Pohl, 1994, p.1016). As a politician and business leader, Escher as a founder, entrenched the organisation inextricably in Swiss banking legislation pertaining to state and banking governance. Consequently, the specific ethos of banking secrecy was further ratified from its original form incepted in the Great Council of Geneva (Guex, 2000). This interdependency between a public corporation and government institutions went as far as Credit Suisse becoming the primary consultant in drafting legal provisions itself (Guex, 2000). Coexisting with the spirit and practical implementation of global, domestic, and geographic neutrality, this regulation became an economic, cultural, and reputational pillar, at home and abroad for Swiss banks and Switzerland.

As would be demanded by shareholders, expanding business and increasing profits will inevitably take a bigger role in the evolution of Credit Suisse, like deposit counters and other financial services related businesses. An interesting development and sign that risk management started to loosen was when several direct ventures incurred relatively immense losses at the time; e.g. Sugar Beet Factory, which may be far removed from the core or extended business of Credit Suisse (Pohl, 1994, p.1016).

PRESENT REALITIES AND CHALLENGES

While banking and finance have their fair share of scandals and financial issues, Credit Suisse stands out due to the scale of its operations and its seeming ability to emerge from these scandals; partly owing to the extent of assets it manages (Clarke, 2014; Financial Stability Board, 2021; US Congress, 2018) and specific provisions in Swiss Federal Act on Banks and Savings Bank, in particular Article 47 (Federal Council of Switzerland, 2022). This article outlines banking secrecy provisions, which shelter Swiss banks from pressures of disclosure to third parties (Guex, 2000). Additionally, included in the spirit of the Swiss Banking Act are

tenets that discourage state intervention, supervision, and inspection apart from exceptional cases in which a semi-state third-party institution is tasked with reviewing situations not explicitly codified in law (Guex, 2000).

Table 1: Post-Financial Crisis Investigations and Events (2008 - 2020), A Partial View (Makortoff & Pegg, 2022; Pegg et al, 2022; Shields et al, 2022; US SEC, 2018)

Date	Event
2008	- Brazilian government investigations
2011	- 2000 job cuts due to weak economic recovery - Four bankers indicted for fraud by U.S. Department of Justice
2012	- US authorities investigations for securities mortgage loans bundling, housing boom risks misrepresentation - Merger of Asset Management and Private Banking
2013	- German authorities investigate German citizen tax evasion
2014 February	- Fined for \$197-M, served 8,500 US clients without registering its activities prompting tax evasion allegations
2014 May	- Pleaded guilty to tax evasion conspiracy in US
2019 August	- Announcement of a new digital "direct banking" business unit under Swiss division
2020 July	- Announcement of Corporate Restructuring

It has become a dilemma to reconcile the unique and atypical circumstances of Credit Suisse, its historical context and key events, with theories and the practical nature of Corporate Governance. While it may be an easier endeavour to select just one event, it would be a disservice to perceiving its unique context. On one hand, the prevailing definitions and practices of Corporate Governance were agreed upon by consensus as a relatively recent discipline, circa 1970 (Cheffins, 2013) for which Credit Suisse pre-dates by more than a century. On the other hand, the concept of governance in its broadest sense -- referring to means and medium of interdependent activities coordination, especially in relation to commercial, legal, and socio-political geographic dimensions (Jessop, 1998) -- definitely applies.

Table 2: Timeline Of Scandals And Controversies (2018 - 2022), A Partial View

Date	Event
2018 July	US Foreign Corrupt Practices Act Violation - \$47-M and \$30-M settlement with US Department of Justice and US Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) respectively. SEC's allegations related to the hiring and promotion of more than a hundred officials from China, violating the Foreign Corrupt Practices Act (US SEC, 2018)
2018 November	Climate Controversy - Investments in fossil fuels companies (SWI, 2020)
2019	Espionage scandal - Discovery of Chief Operating Officer, Pierre-Olivier Bouée, hiring detectives to follow a departing senior management executive if he was enticing clients away from Credit Suisse. COO was removed from office and private investigator committed suicide. (Neate & Kollewe, 2019)
2021 March	Greensill Capital - Closure and liquidation of several supply-chain investment funds tied to Greensill Capital. Investors with approximate assets of \$10-B expected \$3-B in losses as of March 2021. Return of around \$5.9-B to investors with Greensill-associated funds (Bhattacharya & Reddy, 2022)
2021 April	Archegos Capital - Seven executives and others were removed after losses of \$4.7 billion associated with prime brokerage services via Archegos (Glazer et al, 2021; Shields et al, 2022)
2022 February	Bulgarian Drug Money Laundering - Tried in the first criminal trial of a major bank in Switzerland. Swiss prosecutors sought 42 million Swiss francs in compensation from Credit Suisse for enabling cocaine trafficking gang around Evelin Banev in Bulgaria to launder millions of euros circa 2004-2008 (Makortoff & Pegg, 2022; Shields et al, 2022)
2022 February	Suisse Secrets Leak - 30,000 customer details holding over 100-B Swiss francs leaked to the Süddeutsche Zeitung, and became known as "Suisse secrets" (Süddeutsche Zeitung, 2022; Pegg et al, 2022)
2022 February	Russian Oligarchs Loans Documents - After sanctions declared on Russia for the 2022 Invasion of Ukraine, legal requests was issued by Credit Suisse for hedge funds and other investors for destruction of documents linking Russian oligarchs to yacht loans, spawning immense criticism thereafter (Smith, 2022)
2022 October	Social Media Rumours On Bank Demise - Allegations of deepening crisis in the bank that may lead to closure along with correlated event of Hotel Savoy being sold by the bank and other buyback events (Revil, 2011)

We also take an expeditious review of what Credit Suisse already has in place: comprehensive organisational and regulatory sensitive guidelines relating to its Corporate Governance, Board of Directors Independence, Purpose Statements and Code of Conduct, Culture, Strategy, Sustainability Statements, Multispectrum Standing Committees, Audit Functions, and Operational Frameworks, most of which has been long-standing, regularly updated, and regulated by the national regulatory body, i.e. FINMA or the Swiss Financial Market Supervisory Authority (Credit Suisse Group, 2022; Credit Suisse - Executive Board, 2022).

With a more recent time horizon, one remains instilled with cognitive dissonance wading through the complexity of journals, documents, data sets, materials, reports, official news, rumours, statements, and others. Outlined in Table 1 and Table 2 are some of the publicly available events relating to official investigations and reviews as well as controversies and scandals, respectively. Using these points in time as anchors for analysing existing materials, one is met with a proliferation of contemporarily defined corporate governance publications (Financial Stability Board, 2021), legal charters (Federal Council of Switzerland, 2022), national economic as well as sector-specific codes of best practices (economiesuisse, 2016; Swiss Bankers Association, 2022), and professionally prominent groups of people (Credit Suisse - Board of Directors, 2022) leading the charge in running organisations.

Ironically, overlaying (1) the chronology of leadership changes including the demands for achieving top leadership positions, controversies, scandals, and litigation; with (2) the existence of charters and practices of corporate governance that has been rigorously defined at varying levels of industry and implemented as essential requirements for a publicly listed corporation, one may discern a tension emerging from a corporate governance theory perspective (Clarke & Mittal, 2022; Credit Suisse - Executive Board, 2022).

Firstly, there is a clear sensitivity for the importance of Credit Suisse from the perspective of wider society. This is nearly undeniable as a systemically important finance pillar of the international economy and as evidenced by the attention it receives. In addition, purpose, sustainability, corporate social responsibility, and corporate governance frameworks are enshrined in nearly all levels of public corporations in Switzerland. It is in some sense, a tacit context of Swiss regulation (Fedlex, 2022). This manifests a clear public statement that as a corporation, Credit Suisse is not in theory, leaning towards a shareholder primacy model of governance alone (Armour et al, 2003; Blair & Stout, 1999; Clarke, 2014; Palladino & Karlsson, 2019; Stout, 2012a). With this and the structural changes (Monks & Minow, 2011), business model evolution (Coase, 1937), and purpose statements regarding risk, customer care, and risk management, we can conclude a direction towards a multiform and multi-stakeholder

approach to corporate governance while remaining to operate under the close scrutiny of national and international institutions (Alchian & Demsetz, 1973; Clarke, 2004). Secondly and ironically, it seems the challenges and scandals, relentlessly continue even after numerous leadership changes, removal of perpetrators, structural and business strategy changes, and complete overhaul of the corporation and the board in relation to corporate governance issues like lapses in monitoring of risks, abuses by management, and corrupt practices entrenched in the culture (McGrath, 2020; Pegg et al, 2022).

Table 3: Relevance of select corporate governance theories and models to Credit Suisse (Berle & Means, 1932; Coase, 1937; Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Stout, 2012b)

Theory	Relevant	Remarks
Shareholder Primacy Model	Yes	Share prices are sensitive concerns to management which drives business decisions as well as ongoing corporate restructuring and overhaul.
New Institutional Theory	Yes	Firm boundaries are keenly defined along transaction costs of various divisions and geographies as it defines market strategy and corporate structure segregation.
Agency Theory	Yes	Rogue banker activities push the boundaries of acceptable risks, in an environment that is already inherently risk driven.
Managerial Hegemony	No	Regular leadership changes, both individual and wholesale board of director changes happen regularly in response to changes business environment and scandals. Regulatory constraints and operational guidelines confine any attempt of management layers to overpower other stakeholders.
Resource Dependency	Yes	The funding and resources are varied and dynamic. The resources, both investment capital, state intervention, institutional investors, and other social/human capital considerations, are drivers of strategic direction and changes.

FUTURE

A reconciliation of the history and present of Credit Suisse with its future, in terms of its operating temper, corporate governance, and regulatory milieu, produces another perplexity. As we have been recently reminded by the Suisse Leaks (Süddeutsche Zeitung, 2022), Archegos scandal (Glazer et al., 2021), and several U.S. Department of Justice Fraud and Tax Evasion cases (US SEC, 2018), corporate governance is not merely concerned with its varied shareholders and layered managers of the corporation. It engages the wider environment: from governments, public/private institutions, other business entities, and finally towards wider society. Credit Suisse is aware of this, as evidenced by major restructuring that is still ongoing from a purpose, social, business, and governance perspective.

Firstly, the Suisse leaks instruct us of the culture of looking the other way or willful ignorance regarding questionable financial provenance (Makortoff & Pegg, 2022). Despite codes of conduct, risk management, and severe compliance checks prior to onboarding questionable client accounts, some corner cases evade detection or have been overlooked as legacy while regulations change over time. Secondly, the Archegos controversy nudges us to the fact that Credit Suisse, while distinguished often as an example, is just one of many large banks in the world (Glazer et al, 2021) that has fallen victim to abuses of risk management and trust. This is a recurring theme in the understanding of market and financial instability (Konzelmann, 2010) where exploitative practices of rogue bankers or the banking industry unjustly enrich themselves when they get away with it (Cressey, 1954) but are redeemed by bailouts or excused with barely any criminal charges proportionate to the damages they wrought to taxpayers, clients' hard-earned resources, pensions, and the stability of the market itself. Finally, with cases pursued by U.S. institutions, successful exfiltration of criminal information through legal means can only be achieved via diplomatic or coercive state-level actions; albeit, results are sporadic and limited (Emmenegger & Eggenberger, 2018; US SEC 2018). Swiss Banking Secrecy, while some may view it as immoral (Pegg et al, 2022), is ultimately an amoral political and economic mechanism (Guex, 2000; Swiss Bankers Association, 2022) that has taken hundreds of years to develop, in response to geopolitical pressures and the value of the Swiss to remain neutral.

Cognizant of the breadth and depth of information thus far analysed, culture, people, and enforcement are among what is left to benefit from future actionable attention by companies. Fortunately, Credit Suisse has given ample investment in stabilising its guidelines for these concerns which are approved periodically by the government (Credit Suisse Group, 2022). They are also already under increased scrutiny by regulators. Unfortunately, the most challenging aspect of running a corporation is always its most volatile: its people and its culture (Alvesson, 2013; Alvesson & Sveningsson, 2011) and how diligently it will relentlessly enforce all measures to achieve good corporate governance.

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